

Retrofitting a commercial upright microscope to perform micro-transmittance/reflectance spectroscopy

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In the following I will provide a step-by-step guide to supplement a commercial upright metallurgical microscope (**Figure 1**) with the necessary equipment to carry out micro-transmittance and micro-reflectance measurements.

This guide should be considered as a complementary text to Ref. ¹ where many technical details about the micro-transmittance/reflectance technique and setup are described. In that reference, although very thorough, some details about the implementation might be not completely clear.

Figure 1. Picture of the Motic BA310 MET-T optical microscope equipped the modified trinocular to perform micro-transmittance/reflectance measurements.

Trinocular configuration:

The trinocular of the microscope has to be modified to provide two different optical paths: one towards the digital camera and another one towards an optical fiber. Therefore, the conventional trinocular (a tube or a tube lens) should be replaced by some optical and mechanical components.

Table 1. Summary of the optical and mechanical components employed for the modification of the trinocular. Note that the components have been grouped depending on their function to facilitate the identification of the different parts during the assembly.

	Vendor	Part number	Description	Price
Connection to trinocular	Thorlabs	SM1A58	Adaptor microscope trinocular (Nikon) to SM1	72.10 €
		SM1T2	Coupler from SM1A58 to SM1L03	19.01 €
		SM1L03	SM1 Lens Tube	11.05 €
		CCM1-BS013/M	Non-Polarizing Beamsplitter, 400 - 700 nm	261.66 €
		SM1EC2B	Dust Cap for the beamsplitter	9.55 €
Cam arm		SM1V05	Adjustable Lens Tube	27.50 €
		SM1A39	Adaptor from SM1 to C-mount	18.72 €
		SM1T2	Coupler from CCM1-BS013/M to CXY1	19.01 €
Spectrometer arm		CXY1	XY Translating Lens Mount	165.21 €
		SM1T2	Coupler from CXY1 to SM1NR05	19.01 €
		SM1NR05	Focusing stage	175.72 €
	SM05SMA	SMA Fiber Adaptor	26.74 €	
	Subtotal:			825.28 €

All the components are sold by Thorlabs® and therefore the assembly is rather trivial (no special thread adapters or home-made adapters are needed). Simply put the parts together following the scheme shown in **Figure 2**.

In order to have a complete setup we need to add a digital camera to the camera port (necessary to see from which region of the sample we are collecting the reflected/transmitted light) and a spectrometer.

Digital camera:

Regarding the digital camera selection, in Ref. ¹ we installed an Edmund Optics camera (#89-734) but we have now found other more cost-effective options:

Table 2. Digital camera options to supplement the trinocular camera arm.

	Vendor	Part number	Description	Price (€)
OPTION 1	AMScope	MU1803	18 MPix, USM 3.0	366.59
OPTION 2	Aliexpress	EAKINS	21 MPix, USB 2.0 and HDMI outputs. TF Reader	77.88

Figure 2. Detailed scheme of the assembly process of the modified trinocular tube.

Spectrometer:

The spectrometer is the most expensive part of the setup. In Ref. ¹ we installed a broad-band Thorlabs CCD spectrometer but since then we have explored other options that are more cost-effective.

Table3. Different spectrometer and fiber optics options.

	Vendor	Part number	Description	Price (€)
OPTION A	Thorlabs	CCS200/M	Compact CCD Spectrometer 200 nm-1000 nm	2685.45
OPTION B	ASEQ Instruments	LR1-T	Cooled CCD Spectrometer 200 nm – 1100 nm	1065.33
OPTION C	Thunder Optics	SMA-spectrometer	CMOS spectrometer 480 nm – 840 nm	132.5
Fibers	Thorlabs	M15L01	Ø105 µm, 0.22 NA, multimode SMA Fiber, 1 Meter	61.37
		M92L01	Ø200 µm, 0.22 NA, multimode SMA Fiber, 1 Meter	86.19
		M28L01	Ø400 µm, 0.39 NA, multimode SMA Fiber, 1 Meter	82.13

When comparing the performance of the three different spectrometer options, the performance of the Thorlabs CCS200/M is the best followed close by the ASEQ Instruments (that offers an excellent trade-off between its performance and cost). The ASEQ Instruments LR1-T is deep-cooled what allows one to integrate for longer time periods than with the Thorlabs CCS200/M.

Figure 3 compares the micro-reflectance spectra acquired onto the same single-, bi- and tri-layer MoS₂ flakes mechanically exfoliated onto a Gel-Film® substrate. The Thorlabs and the ASEQ spectrometers provide almost the same results but the spectra acquired with the ASEQ system present some little artificial features at ~750 nm (arousing most likely from the sorting filter). Although the Thunder Optics system allows to resolve the A and B excitons of MoS₂ (and the redshift of the A exciton upon thickness increase)²⁻⁵ the magnitude of the micro-reflectance is systematically lower than that measured with the other two systems. Therefore, the Thunder Optics spectrometer might be a good option for applications that don't require a quantitative analysis of the reflectance and transmittance magnitude but a quantitative analysis of the wavelength (like position of absorption edges or excitons).

Figure 3. Comparison between the micro-reflectance spectra acquired with the three different spectrometer options on the same single-, bi- and tri-layer MoS₂ flakes. In all three cases the spectra display the dips related to the A (~660 nm) and B (~605 nm) excitons.

Total cost of the different configurations

Configuration	Description	Price
1A	Modified trinocular + USB 3.0 camera + Thorlabs spectrometer	3877.32 €
1B	Modified trinocular + USB 3.0 camera + ASEQ spectrometer	2257.20 €
1C	Modified trinocular + USB 3.0 camera + Thunder Opt. spectrometer	1324.37 €
2A	Modified trinocular + USB 2.0 camera + Thorlabs spectrometer	3601.39 €
2B	Modified trinocular + USB 2.0 camera + ASEQ spectrometer	1981.27 €
2C	Modified trinocular + USB 2.0 camera + Thunder Opt. spectrometer	1048.44 €

References

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